

Dynamic building performance gap related to occupant behaviors: A framework to predict the impacts of possible causal factors

Ahmad Esmailzadeh^{*}, Mohamed Hamdy

Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Building Performance Gap
Occupant Behavior
Neuro-fuzzy Model
Energy Simulation
Nearly-zero energy building

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to develop a prediction framework for minimizing Building Performance Gaps (BPGs) considering the frequent dynamics in non-residential buildings by quantifying the impacts of occupant behavior (OB) parameters. The framework is designed as an extension to existing building performance simulation tools, enabling the quantification of OB discrepancies between design-stage predictions and operational outcomes. Through detailed simulation analyses across eight standard building models, we examine the influence of three independent OB parameters: occupancy schedules, occupancy activities, and setpoint temperatures. Among these, setpoint temperature is identified as the main OB parameter in determining energy demand based on duration curve of different standard models. While the occupancy schedules and activities have negligible impact on peak power demand, they contribute significantly to the energy performance gap (up to 50 %) and deviations in indoor air temperature (up to 5 %). We develop and train the neuro-fuzzy prediction model using the results of simulation-based analysis to estimate the effects of each OB parameters in BPGs. The prediction framework is validated using a calibrated case study, where results demonstrate an improvement of 16.24 % in energy performance prediction and 5 % in indoor temperature estimation compared to standard simulations. While the framework effectively increases simulation accuracy in predicting building frequency energy performances, it is currently limited to simulation-based evaluations.

1. Introduction

Energy usage plays a critical role in climate change mitigation and is central to socioeconomic development [1]. By growing the global shift toward sustainable development, the building sector plays an integral part in manipulating energy demand [2]. Consequently, the European Union has employed policies and programs to promote the energy performance of buildings [3]. Developing regulations and standards for various types of buildings is a part of union policies to lead the building sector in enhancing energy efficiency [4]. While multiple standards and rating systems aim to promote resource efficiency, the performance of buildings in actual implementation generally fails to meet design predictions. This phenomenon represents the importance of the difference between the predicted performance in the design phase and

measurements in the operational phase, referred to as the Building Performance Gap (BPG) [5], and when related specifically to energy, as the Building Energy Performance Gap (BEPG) [6].

When BPG occurs, the core objectives of green building initiatives and energy-efficient strategies may be compromised [7]. Concerns about BPG problem trace back to the early 1980s, and interest in BPG has grown in recent decades [8,9]. However the BPG is not limited to BEPG, the significant role of energy-efficient buildings in reducing global energy consumption has highlighted the need to address BEPG [10]. According to the IEA EBC Annex 53, the causes of BEPGs can be broadly classified into physical and human-influenced factors [11]. Physical-influenced factors include building envelopes, climate, and building services. Human-influenced factors constitute building occupants and occupancy-related variables like Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).

Abbreviations: BEPG, Building Energy Performance Gap; BPG, Building Performance Gap; IEQ, Indoor Environmental Quality; EPW, EnergyPlus Weather; HDD, Heating Degree Days; CDD, Cooling Degree Days; AI, Artificial Intelligence; ABM, agent-based modeling; nZEB, nearly zero-energy buildings; LOI, Level-of-Information; ML, Machine Learning; POE, post-occupancy evaluation; OFAT, One Factor at a Time; VBSA, Variance-Based Sensitivity Analysis; DEUI, Daily Energy Use Index; TMY, Typical Meteorological Year; OD, Occupancy Density; MR, Metabolic Rate; SA, Sensitivity Analysis; EUI, Energy Use Intensity; KPI, Key Performance Indicator; AHU, Air Handling Unit; VAV, Variable Air Volume; IQR, InterQuartile Range; ANOVA, Analysis of Variance; SS, Sum of Squares; MS, Mean Squares.

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ahmad.esmailzadeh@NTNU.no (A. Esmailzadeh).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2025.116340>

Received 24 June 2025; Received in revised form 19 August 2025; Accepted 20 August 2025

Available online 21 August 2025

0378-7788/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Fishbone analysis of building energy performance gap.

Despite the efforts of the scientific community, the impacts of these factors on BEPG remain unclear [12]. Therefore, analyzing the impacts of different factors on BEPG lead us to develop solutions for closing BPG.

Several attempts have been made to analyze the root causes of BEPG. From the perspective of building simulations, BEPG is attributed to inappropriate settings parameters in four main aspects: weather, building envelope, system performance, and occupant behavior [13]. Firstly, inaccuracies in weather data of dynamic simulations effect on BEPG [3,6,12,14]. Zare et al. mentioned that a corrected EnergyPlus Weather (EPW) file resulted in a 6.6 % reduction in BEPG [15]. Reguis et al. implemented four different test reference year weather files to evaluate the relationship between BEPG and low-temperature heat. This approach helps them to consider the possible deviations in building energy requirement at the design step [16]. Inaccuracy in modeling the cold and hot weather conditions is mentioned in [17] as the main causes of BEPG. In their framework for closing BEPG, comparing the Heating Degree Days (HDD) and Cooling Degree Days (CDD) in modeling and real conditions are mentioned to represent the role of weather data in BEPG [17]. As the other main aspects, building envelopes are investigated during various conditions to evaluate their deviation impacts on BEPG [18,19]. The energy performance of a building depends largely on the ability of its envelope to resist heat transmission, determined by the coefficient of heat transfer rate [16]. Inaccuracy in inputs and assumptions for calculating the rate of heat transfer across an envelope resulted in deviations in building modelling and actual energy consumption [6]. Alam et al. classify the material and equipment of buildings as a group of risk factors in construction, resulting in BPG [20]. Within the construction stage, changing the construction quality resulted in differencing the heat transfer across envelopes from the design stage, which is known as the critical cause of BEPG [21,22]. By implementing simulation based sensitivity analysis approach, the three key factors affecting annual cooling energy use are identified, including window size, the building orientation and the glazing solar transmittance [23]. The performance and settings of heating and cooling systems are cited as other factors that influence the BEPG [5,24]. Mistakes in installation and malfunctions of the engineering system contribute to the difference between equipment efficiency and the actual efficiency of the systems [25]. Equipment failures and aging result in changes to the performance of heating and cooling systems. These deviations in system efficiency lead buildings to experience BEPG [26,27]. Occupancies play an integral

role in building energy simulation in the design step, yet studies investigating the influence of model types and their input assumptions remain sparse [28,29]. Comparing the results of the actual occupancy scenario, standard scenario, and default scenario of DesignBuilder demonstrates the potential for up to 36 % error in calculating energy consumption [30]. Simanic et al. assess the influence of user-related parameters on building energy consumption and find that 33 % of measured energy usage depends on these parameters [31]. Fig. 1 demonstrates the main causes of the performance gap from dynamic simulation perspective concluded from ref. [13].

Among these, OB is the least predictable and most complex, making it a key focus area in recent studies [32]. Therefore, our paper focuses on human-influenced factors. By considering the findings of reference [13] on occupant behavior, six main parameters related to occupancy are defined, resulting in a building performance gap from a dynamic simulation perspective. Analyzing the role of occupancy in buildings by investigating various assumptions and parameters provides the opportunity of enhancing the simulation role in energy calculations and closing the performance gap between actual consumption and estimated one.

1.1. Literature reviews

The literature review and background knowledge of the research is provided in this section. By considering the definition of BPG, various studies have assessed the impacts of different parameters on buildings' performances. While these studies evaluated the buildings' performances in various uncertain parameters related to occupancies, their evaluations are limited to case studies. Implementing sensitivity analysis for occupancy behaviors and developing an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based model for predicting the impacts of occupancies on BPG have been investigated less during previous studies. (See Table 1)

In all the studies reviewed, occupant behaviors are recognized as a significant factor contributing to BPG. However, the statistic patterns of these behaviors have led to simulations that use a simplified occupancy model, resulting in uncertain outcomes compared to actual operating conditions. Consequently, modeling occupant behaviors has garnered significant interest from researchers over the past decade. Most studies remain narrow in focus, often concentrating only on developing occupant behavior models for specific case studies or regional buildings.

Table 1
Summary of research/review papers related to the role of occupancies in building performance gap.

Reference	Year	Study Parameters	Building Type	Location	Climate	Main viewpoint/findings
[22]	2012	Energy consumption for lighting, small power, and catering; post-occupancy evaluation; predictive modeling	Office	UK	Temperate	Demonstrated that post-occupancy evaluation (POE) data improves predictive energy modeling accuracy to within 3 % of actual usage.
[33]	2017	Occupant behavior, heating/cooling set-points, energy use for equipment, lighting, DHW, ventilation rates, window blinds	Residential	Italy	Humid Subtropical Climate	Highlighted significant energy variations in nearly zero-energy buildings (nZEB)s due to occupant behavior and emphasized the need for improved occupant behavior models.
[34]	2020	Sociotechnical analysis of space utilization, adaptation of equipment by building operator, and their impacts on energy performance	Education	France	Temperate	Emphasized that misfits between design and space occupancy hinder energy optimization and comfort experience in buildings.
[35]	2020	Occupant behavior data, energy performance gap analysis, agent-based modeling (ABM) for behavior simulation	office	Pakistan	Hot and arid	Identified a performance gap in energy-efficient buildings caused by occupant behavior. Simulated behavior modification through interventions and achieved potential energy savings of 25.4 %.
[36]	2021	Occupancy schedule	Residential	Singapore	Tropical	Showed 13 % reduction in BEPG using more accurate occupancy schedules based on WiFi connection counts.
[37]	2022	Heating set point, heating schedule, window opening schedule, plug loads, occupant behavior analysis	Residential	UK	Temperate	Found that increasing heating period during daily schedules, window openings, and plug loads reduces the energy performance gap to <15 %. Highlighted occupant behavior as a key factor and recommended better data collection for modeling.
[38]	2022	Hybrid modeling combining first-principles (physics-based) and machine learning models for energy prediction	Commercial building	China	Subtropical	A hybrid approach integrating simulation and Machine Learning (ML) proposed to minimize energy performance gaps. Introduced the Level-of-Information (LOI) concept for balancing model detail and accuracy.
[39]	2023	Indoor air temperature, relative humidity, air change rate, TVOC levels, energy simulations	Residential	Italy	Humid Subtropical Climate	Analyzed the impact of retrofits on energy performance gaps, revealing contrasting behaviors among user groups affecting ventilation and temperature settings.
[40]	2024	Stochastic behavior patterns, occupancy schedules	Residential	Jordan	Semi-Arid	Represented the impacts of dynamic schedules on energy use with emphasizing on occupant behavior and realistic schedules for improving building performance prediction.
[41]	2024	Energy performance gap, energy signature diagrams	Residential	Hungary	Continental	Illustrated an average 28 % performance gap due to differences between simulation and measured data. The increased occupancy presence due to COVID was examined and showed no-change in daily district heating consumption.
[42]	2024	Occupant behavior, building operational patterns related to behavior	Residential	China	Various	Clustered operational patterns based on occupancy behaviors and established a comprehensive occupant behavior database
[43]	2024	Sensitivity analysis of buildings characteristic and HVAC specification	School	Norway	Cold	Found that BMS of HVAC plays an integral part in reducing operational cost as well as providing comfort condition. The simulation is designed based on fixed occupancy pattern as the baseline and real data for training algorithm.
[44]	2024	Occupant behavior, reinforcement learning trained by stochastic interactions and external environment	Public Buildings	China	Various	Represented reinforcement learning for modeling occupancy behavior, highlighting benefits in reducing building performance gap.
[45]	2024	Exploring the impacts of causal factors and effect factors of BEPG	Mixed	China	Various	Indicated that there were six most significant factors were
[46]	2024	Performance gap in Korean BEEC-certified buildings	Non-residential	South Korea	Temperate	setting errors in simulation, including occupant behavior Mentioned that building energy certification is a rating, not a prediction because of unpredictable and stochastic behavior of building energy systems and occupants
[47]	2025	Occupant behavior, causal and data sufficiency in developing robust model for occupant behavior	Residential	South Korea	Temperate	Improved building performance simulations by modeling intercausal occupant behaviors with Bayesian networks.

There are relatively few studies in the context of SA of occupancy parameters that provide a prediction framework for BPG based on simulation-based analysis.

To create a comprehensive framework for nonresidential buildings, we simulated eight standard use cases under various stochastic occupancy parameters. Much of the current literature on BPG emphasizes the development of models for occupant behavior. We assess the role of occupancy parameters by implementing two different SA methods, and the stochastic occupancy parameters developed for SA are incorporated into a training prediction model developed by neuro-fuzzy algorithm.

1.2. Research gap

Even when a building is designed and used correctly, occupant behavior characterization challenges building energy performance [48]. Although recent literature increasingly acknowledges the role of occupant behavior in BPGs, quantitative analyses that assess the sensitivity of BPGs to OB parameters remain unclear [49]. In particular, long-term sensitivity analyses that account for stochastic variability in occupant behavior and integrate these insights into predictive frameworks are limited. Moreover, current research often focuses on case-specific models rather than scalable, generalizable solutions. Evaluating building performances and the role of OB as a source of uncertainty in

Fig. 2. Framework for building performance gap analysis – role of occupancies.

Table 2
Small hotel prototype building information [53].

Small hotel	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	3,725
Unconditioned	288
Total	4,013
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Steel-frame walls with 2x4 studs at 16 in. on center
Exterior Layer	1-inch stucco
Interior Layers	5/8-inch gypsum board on both sides, with wall insulation sandwiched between these layers
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	6 groups
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	132

frequent system assessments, rather than relying solely on annual evaluations, illustrates previously unpredicted impacts on energy flexibility and grid control conditions.

A search of the literature revealed a few studies that analyzed the role of occupancy parameters in BPG. Implementing sensitivity analysis on occupancy parameters has led to the development of an algorithm for closing the role of occupancy in the simulation uncertainty. Not much attention has been given to the sensitivity analysis of occupancy parameters in the long-term study of buildings. There is also no established method that combines long-term simulation-based sensitivity analysis with machine learning algorithms to create a prediction framework for occupancy impacts on BEPG and IEQ gap at each time step. This study aims to fill this gap by creating a framework to analyze the sensitivity of BPG to occupancy parameters as a first step. The ultimate goal is to develop a predictive framework to determine the role of occupancy parameters in BEPG and IEQ.

1.3. Contributions

This study set out to develop a framework for predicting the impact of occupancy on BPGs using a neuro-fuzzy learning approach. This highlights the importance of understanding how sensitive BPG is to occupancy parameters. We conducted two different sensitivity analyses: One Factor at a Time (OFAT) and Variance-Based Sensitivity Analysis (VBSA). The inputs and outputs of these sensitivity analysis approaches were used to train a neuro-fuzzy model for predicting the impact of occupancy on BPGs. Implementing the prediction model and simulation results of the buildings in parallel will improve the theoretical calculations of building energy performance and subsequently reduce the BPGs. The key contributions of this study are as follows:

- 1- Simulation based sensitivity analysis: Implementation of both OFAT and VBSA methods to quantify the impact of occupancy parameters on BPGs in non-residential buildings.
- 2- Diverse Building Typologies: Investigation of eight standardized non-residential building use cases across five categories (office, school, hospital, hotel, and restaurant) to ensure broad applicability.
- 3- Long-term sensitivity analysis of occupancy parameters in various low-energy buildings BEPG and IEQ gap.
- 4- Creating a framework to develop a model based on neuro-fuzzy algorithm for predicting the impact of occupancy on BEPG and IEQ gap: The inputs and outputs of OFAT and VBSA are implemented to

train a neuro-fuzzy model for predicting the impact of occupancy parameters on BPG.

- 5- Assessment of prediction framework and neuro-fuzzy model based on a validated simulation.

We conducted studies on five categories of buildings, including eight different standard use cases, using the EnergyPlus model [50]. Based on the available standard models in Energyplus, nonresidential buildings are categorized to school, office, hospital, hotel, and restaurant. We also consider a general category for buildings without specific relation to the mentioned categories. All use cases are designed based on ASHRAE 90.1 2016 and represented as prototype building models at [51]. We implemented two sensitivity analysis approaches to evaluate the impacts of occupancy parameters in different use cases. To investigate the one-year simulation of buildings on different occupancy conditions, EnergyPlus/SIMULINK co-simulation is used [52]. The results of simulations are utilized to train the BPG neuro-fuzzy prediction model. By considering the variety of buildings' categories, this study plays a key role in providing a comprehensive prediction framework to close BPG by reducing uncertainty in buildings related to occupancy behaviors.

The remaining part of the paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 represents the methodology including, use cases, EnergyPlus models, considered parameters in each use case, and the parameters domain in simulation. Then, the sensitivity analysis approaches, and AI-based model for predicting BPGs are described. The results of sensitivity analysis and the potential of AI-based model in predicting the impacts of occupancies' behaviors on BEPG and IEQ gap are investigated in section 3. Section 4 presents key findings and takeaways based on the results. Finally, the research achievements are concluded in section 5.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the methodology used in this research. A suite of standardized prototype models from EnergyPlus was selected to represent five building typologies, including office, school, hospital, hotel, and restaurant. Each category includes multiple use cases, reflecting variation in scale and occupancy patterns. By conducting detailed simulations of case studies, we have defined the training data. This training data is utilized to create a prediction model using a neuro-fuzzy algorithm. Fig. 2 structures a framework for performing a parametric analysis and developing the prediction model of the building performance gap, which assesses the role of occupancy parameters in non-residential buildings.

2.1. Representative simulation models

According to Fig. 2, the first step of the framework is defined to create representative simulations model. Baseline models relying on ASHRAE 90.1 standard are defined, alongside benchmarking models based on building typologies. By considering the variety of available models in EnergyPlus, 5 main benchmarking models are considered including, hotel, health center, office, school, and restaurant.

2.2. Benchmarking

The buildings' models are classified in benchmarks based on building functions and representative types. The initial benchmarks are defined by existing models in EnergyPlus, listed as hotel, health center, office, school, and restaurant, while it could be extended to more use cases. For example, when implementing this framework to predict the performance gap of an airport, the terminal category may not be included in the initial benchmarks. Therefore, in addition to defined benchmarks, a general model is developed to enable the prediction of other types of benchmarks. Since the general model is developed using data from all categories, it enhances the comprehensiveness of the framework by allowing it to cover all types of buildings. The main five categories of

Table 3
Large hotel prototype building information [53].

Large hotel	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	11,345
Unconditioned	0
Total	11,345
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Mass walls with 8-inch Concrete Masonry Units (CMU), and wall insulation
Interior Layers	0.5-inch gypsum board
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	2 groups
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

Table 4
Hospital prototype building information [53].

Hospital	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	22,436
Unconditioned	0
Total	22,436
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Mass walls with 8-inch heavyweight concrete, and wall insulation
Interior Layers	0.5-inch gypsum board
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	2 groups
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

benchmarks are considered by: hotel, health center, office, school, and restaurant. Using the ASHRAE 90.1 model in EnergyPlus, a 1-year simulation of at least one use case in each benchmark is simulated. Based on the importance of office and hotel and according to availability of models, we investigated 2 various sizes of hotels and 3 different sizes of office in benchmark simulation. The prototype building models with detailed information are represented in [53].

2.2.1. Hotel

Two sizes of hotel are considered based on prototype building models: small and large.

– Small hotel

4 story building including 67 thermal zones are simulated as small hotel. The window to wall ratio is equal to 10.9 % in the prototype. The hotel includes guest rooms which is residential and the other areas which are not residential. More details about building summary and occupancy conditions are represented in Table 2.

Table 5
Small office prototype building information [53].

Small office	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	511
Unconditioned	568 (Attic)
Total	1,079
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Wood-frame walls with 2x4 studs at 16 in. on center
Exterior Layer	1-inch stucco
Interior Layers	5/8-inch gypsum board on both sides, with wall insulation sandwiched between these layers
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	1 group
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

Table 6
Medium office prototype building information [53].

Medium office	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	4,982
Unconditioned	0
Total	4,982
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Steel-Frame walls with 2x4 studs at 16 in. on center
Exterior Layer	0.4-inch stucco
Interior Layers	5/8-inch gypsum board on both sides, with wall insulation sandwiched between these layers
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	1 group
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

– Large hotel

A large hotel prototype is considered a building with 6 above-ground floors plus one basement including 195 thermal zones. The large hotel consists of 179 guest rooms, which are mentioned as residential parts of the building. The window fraction is considered equal to 26.6 % for this building. More details are represented in Table 3, notifying the building summary and occupancy conditions.

2.2.2. Health center

The health center is mentioned as the other building benchmark in the framework. A 5-story hospital building including 162 thermal zones is simulated in the investigation. The residential part of the building constitutes 103 patient rooms. The window fraction is mentioned in [53] as equal to 14.6 % for this building prototype. The hospital details information is demonstrated in Table 4.

2.2.3. Office

To evaluate the performance of offices as a benchmark of

Table 7
Large office prototype building information [53].

Large office	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	46,320
Unconditioned	0
Total	46,320
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Mass walls with 8-inch heavyweight concrete, and wall insulation
Interior Layers	0.5-inch gypsum board
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	1 group
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

Table 8
School prototype building information [53].

Secondary school	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	19,592
Unconditioned	0
Total	19,592
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Steel-Frame walls with 2x4 studs at 16 in. on center
Exterior Layer	0.4-inch stucco
Interior Layers	5/8-inch gypsum board on both sides, with wall insulation sandwiched between these layers
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	6 groups
Group Schedule	6 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays during study periods and summer holiday
Metabolic Rate	120

nonresidential building, this group is divided into 3 use cases according to the size of buildings.

– Small office

A flat building with 6 thermal zones is simulated to evaluate the small office conditions. Window to wall ratio is considered equivalent to 21.2 % based on [53] building prototype. Table 5 shows the details of small office in our investigation.

– Medium office

The medium office is simulated based on a 3-story building, including 18 thermal zones. Window fraction is equal to 33.0 % based on [53] for this type of building. Table 6 demonstrates the details of building summary and occupancy conditions in medium office simulation.

– Large office

Table 9
Restaurant prototype building information [53].

Full-service restaurant	
<i>Area (m²)</i>	
Conditioned	511
Unconditioned	511 (Attic)
Total	1,022
<i>Wall construction</i>	
Structural Frame	Steel-Frame wall
Exterior Layer	1-inch stucco
Interior Layers	0.625-inch gypsum board on both sides, with wall insulation sandwiched between these layers
<i>Occupancy condition</i>	
No. occupancy group	1 group
Group Schedule	3 schedules, including working days, Saturdays, and Sundays
Metabolic Rate	120

The prototype for a large office is modeled after a 12-floor building that comprises 86 thermal zones [53]. The maximum window fraction for office group is related to large office equal to 38.1 %. Details regarding occupancy conditions and the building's construction can be found in Table 7, which pertains to the large office prototype.

2.2.4. School

The school category is the other building benchmark investigated in this study. The secondary school prototype building in [53], which includes 2 floors and 46 thermal zones, is considered the school benchmark's use case. In this prototype, the window fraction is equivalent to 35 %. The details of occupancy conditions and building construction summary are represented in Table 8.

2.2.5. Restaurant

The other nonresidential category mentioned in the framework is restaurant prototype building. According to [53], a full-service restaurant is designed based on a flat building, including 2 conditioned thermal zones and 1 unconditioned thermal zone. The window-to-wall ratio is determined equal to 17.1 % in the prototype building design. Table 9 demonstrates details data regarding the restaurant and its occupancies.

2.3. Removing climate role

To accurately assess the energy performance of benchmark models, it is necessary to ensure that the energy consumption data are comparable across different buildings and weather conditions. This comparability is achieved through normalization, which removes the effects of weather variations and differences in building size [54]. The Daily Energy Use Index (DEUI) is calculated as the normalized energy consumption per unit floor area and per degree day (HDD and CDD), allowing fair comparison between models regardless of building size or climatic conditions. Although the DEUI is expressed on a daily basis, the normalization is intended for cross-case comparability. The EPW file for Denver, based on the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) from 2009 to 2023, is used in all simulations of use cases. Consequently, the HDD and CDD from this weather data are utilized in the calculation of the DEUI represented in Fig. 3.

According to the weather data demonstrated in Fig. 3, the use cases heating season are defined from October to May while the cooling season are determined from June to September. The annual CDD and HDD are implemented in calculating DEUI of use cases.

Fig. 3. Weather information of Denver based on TMY data.

Fig. 4. The training data of prediction model based on simulating representative use cases.

To eliminate the influence of buildings' sizes, the detailed data of use cases are required. Therefore, we consider the area of each use case when calculating DEUI.

2.4. Creating model for prediction

The inputs and outputs of the prediction model are defined based on

OB uncertainties and the objectives of the model. Six OB-related parameters are identified, including occupancy schedule, temperature setpoint, ventilation, hot water, internal heat gain, and electrical appliance usage.[13]. In this study, only the independent parameters are evaluated to reduce the number of investigated variables. Accordingly, the dependent parameters are mentioned as follows:

Fig. 5. A) timeseries trend, b) variability, and c) distribution of od related to small office building in different scenarios.

- 1- Ventilation demand: the ventilation rates are adjusted based on CO₂ concentration and occupancy levels [55]. Consequently, the demand for ventilation is linked to Occupancy Density (OD) and occupant activities.
- 2- Hot water demand: water usage fluctuates during simulations based on the number of occupants and their activities [56]. Therefore, it could be considered a dependent parameter to OD and occupant activities.
- 3- Internal heat gain: internal heat gain is calculated based on heat generated by occupants, electrical appliances, and lighting that contributes to the overall thermal load [57]. By considering the non-

- residential buildings' equipment, the occupancy-related heat gain is a dependent variable to OD and their activities.
- 4- Electrical appliance usage: Occupancy in non-residential buildings requires energy for equipment, lighting, and personal appliances [58]. By considering the facility management system, electrical usage is directly connected to operating hours during the simulation period which is related to occupancy schedules.

Therefore, the OB-related parameters can be summarized as occupancy schedules, occupancy activities, and temperature setpoints. Accordingly, the framework inputs are defined based on occupants'

Fig. 5. (continued).

schedules, occupants' metabolic rate (MR), and the setpoint temperature. Since the setpoint temperature is determined by the facility management system, boundary values are applied to quantify the maximum uncertainties related to this parameter.

The primary objectives of the prediction model are to quantify the DEUI gap and the indoor air temperature gap, mentioned as the outputs. Accordingly, the model is designed to estimate these gaps based on the defined input parameters.

2.4.1. Training /Verification datasets

Considering the mentioned benchmarks and use cases, a representative sample of hourly timestep data is created for a one-year simulation. Based on the occupancy-related parameters in each use case, the training data is generated by use case simulation for developing a prediction model. Since the use cases involve multiple occupancy groups, occupancy schedules are defined separately for each group.

In this study, two sensitivity analysis approaches are implemented to create stochastic inputs, including OFAT and VBSA. OFAT is a straightforward local approach that isolates the effect of each input by varying one parameter across its full range while holding others fixed. This provides a clear understanding of the direct impact of individual inputs on model outputs. However, OFAT does not account for parameter interactions, which are often significant in nonlinear building performance models. To address this limitation, VBSA is employed as a global method that evaluates the contribution of each parameter and their interactions by sampling across the entire input space [59,60]. Accordingly, VBSA provides more robust sensitivity measures in the presence of nonlinearities and non-additive effects [61]. We implement OFAT to evaluate the primary influence of each parameter, as well as VBSA to identify higher-order effects and interactions. Using both methods ensures a balanced analysis and offering a comprehensive justification of parameters in relation to building performance gaps.

Stochastic input data for OD and MR were generated using both random and Sobol sequences to support OFAT and VBSA methodologies. DEUI and indoor air temperature are evaluated under these stochastic conditions. The difference between the standard simulation and the

random occupancy conditions are calculated as the BPGs. Outputs from these simulations are then employed as the training datasets for a neuro-fuzzy prediction model, developed to quantify deviations in DEUI and indoor air temperature resulting from OB-related variability.

In addition to stochastic conditions shown in Fig. 4, the boundaries for setpoint temperature are implemented in simulation to determine the impact of setpoint temperature in BPGs. The study implements data from five different benchmarks, consisting of eight use cases with different occupancy groups and MR schedules. These schedules were defined over 8,760 timesteps (hourly) for MR and occupancy groups' presence schedules. The definition approaches are developed based on random and Sobol functions for OFAT and VBSA, respectively. For general benchmark training, all available training data for the various benchmarks is utilized. Thus, following VBSA approach, a total of 70,080 samples are used for training.

Based on random and Sobol functions, the inputs of models related to occupancy schedules and MRs of occupancy are generated. Fig. 5 represents the generated data regarding to OD of small office building (as a sample data) by mentioned approaches. The baseline and random activity function follow almost the same schedule. The difference between these two inputs is related to the vacation and Saturday working hours which is neglected in random activity simulation.

Fig. 5 data variations demonstrate different models of OD used to introduce diverse patterns in the training prediction model. Fig. 5a illustrates the trends of OD in the small office over a simulation period, as a result of implementing different schedules. Baseline scenarios and random activity follow working hours schedules with a constant pattern. Random occupancy schedule and Sobol function show scattered low-to-medium density values and structured randomness, respectively. The boxplot in Fig. 5b presents the variability in OD for the four scenarios. As the baseline and random activity follow the constant pattern of occupancy schedules, the boxplots of their OD exhibit negligible variability with near the upper bound average because of working hours in defined standard schedule. The random and Sobol functions demonstrate greater variability, with wider interquartile ranges and extended whiskers. The histogram graph, Fig. 5c, of OD under four scenarios highlights this

Fig. 6. A) timeseries trend, b) variability, and c) distribution of mr related to small office building in different scenarios.

input distribution. The baseline and random activity scenarios switch occupancy schedules based on working hours without any distribution during working periods. By focusing on working hours, random occupancy schedules and Sobol function have flatter distributions, showing lower density clusters and higher variability across bins. The defined occupancy schedules are designed to replicate realistic and extreme scenarios for training prediction model, ensuring robust model performance across different operational conditions.

The other investigated parameter related to occupancy behavior is MR schedule during the simulation period. Fig. 6 illustrates the timeseries, variability, and distribution of MR generated by random and Sobol functions as well as baseline value of standard simulations for small office building (as a sample data). According to ANSI/ASHRAE Standard

55 [62], the MR of occupancies in nonresidential buildings during various activities values in the range of 40–220 W/m². Therefore, the random and Sobol functions are defined to cover almost all the range during simulation period. The baseline and Random occupancy scenario implement MR equal to 120 W/m² based on the small office prototype building developed in [53].

The variation and distribution of MR during various scenarios simulation are demonstrated in Fig. 6. The scatter plot shown in Fig. 6a represents the MR resulting from occupancies' behaviors across 1-year simulation by hourly frequency. The baseline scenario and random occupancy schedule aligned with a constant metabolic rate equal to 120 W/m². Random activity schedule and Sobol function generate stochastic variability and structured randomness, respectively. The MR based on

Fig. 6. (continued).

Fig. 7. Architecture of neuro-fuzzy prediction model.

Table 10
Large commercial building heat transfer coefficient [66].

Surface	$U \left(\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot C} \right)$
Exterior Wall	0.552
Roof	1.961
Floor	9.596
Medium Floor	19.193
Wall (Metal Panel)	0.394

random and Sobol functions are distributed around a median metabolic rate (~120 W/m²) with a bounded range (approximately 50 to 190 W/m²), representing dynamic human activities. Fig. 6b illustrates the

variability of MR shown the similarity of this parameter generated by random and Sobol functions. The histogram distribution of MR in Fig. 6c ensures an evenly distributed coverage across the metabolic rate range by Sobol function. Accordingly, the metabolic rate inputs cover the diversity and complexity of possible occupancies' behaviors for prediction model training.

In nonresidential buildings, the setpoints of thermal zones are usually determined by facility management approaches. The facility manager adjusts the indoor temperature to align with the occupants' comfort preferences, which can fluctuate during the simulation and significantly influence Energy Use Intensity (EUI) and DEUI. To consider this parameter in this study, the analysis includes simulating the building at both the lower and upper bounds of thermal comfort. In addition to the standard comfort level of 22 °C, the use cases' performances are assessed

Table 11
HVAC system of commercial case study.

System	Equipment	Specification	Quantity (Number)	Connection with Other resources
Distribution	Air handlers hot/cold deck	Air Handling Units (AHUs) – Variable Air Volume (VAV)	58	The required electricity is supplied by CCHP, BIPV, and power grid.
Heating	Hot water boiler	21,980 kW Efficiency – 87 %	8	
Cooling	Chiller	4,500-ton Capacity COP – 3	5	
CCHP	Micro CCHP	Maximum power – 100 kW Nominal frequency – 68,000 rpm lower heating value – 27.216 kJ	1	Designed by [67] – Connect to initial HVAC system – Preheating of heating system, supplying electricity of cooling system
BIPV	double-glazed polycrystalline glaze	Total area – 210 square meter	NA	Connect to initial HVAC system

at 20 °C and 24 °C, representing the lowest and highest thermal comfort thresholds, respectively.

2.4.2. Neuro-fuzzy prediction model

After implementing the SA and developing the training data, the prediction model is generated using a neuro-fuzzy method. In this study, neuro-fuzzy models are created to predict the DEUI gap and the indoor air temperature gap for each benchmark as the IEQ parameter. The inputs are classified into three levels based on the constant ranges defined in the membership functions. Each level's membership function is defined using the Gaussian method. The membership functions, as well as the inputs and outputs, are consistent for both Random and Sobol input generation. Fig. 7 illustrates the layered architecture of the neuro-fuzzy prediction model.

According to Fig. 7, each occupancy group contributes to OD as the input for the prediction model. Occupancy MR is defined as the impact of occupancy activities within the simulation. Therefore, a normalized MR based on building area and OD is incorporated into the prediction model. The DEUI gap and the indoor air temperature gap between the standard model and the uncertain model are identified as the outputs of the prediction model. In the final step, by adjusting the standard model based on the predicted gaps, the expected outputs are calculated.

2.5. Verification

The training process integrated data from five building categories and different operational conditions, which allowed the model to represent a wide range of variability in energy performance. An independent building case is used for validation to assess the predictive power and robustness of the proposed Framework. The use of neuro-fuzzy prediction model strengthens the framework, as neuro-fuzzy model has been demonstrated in previous studies to provide high adaptability and robustness in handling nonlinear and uncertain parameters in building energy systems [63,64]. Considering DEUI gap and indoor air temperature gap as the outputs of prediction model led the framework to cover different sizes of buildings based on the normalization results. This integration ensures that the developed model is not only reliable but also transferable across building archetypes and climatic contexts.

To evaluate the prediction model, a calibrated shoe case model is analyzed based on the role of specific occupancy parameters (OD

resulting from occupancies' schedule, MR, and setpoint) in contributing to the performance gap. The testing procedure involved the following steps:

- 1- Simulating the calibrated shoebox model under standard conditions and evaluating hourly DEUI and indoor air temperature over a one-year period.
- 2- Simulating the same model under stochastic conditions and evaluating hourly DEUI and indoor air temperature.
- 3- Running the neuro-fuzzy prediction model under stochastic conditions to estimate the hourly DEUI and indoor air temperature gaps.
- 4- Integrating the results from Step 1 and Step 3.
- 5- Comparing the results from Steps 1, 2, and 4 to demonstrate the potential of the prediction model in enhancing the accuracy of building simulation tools.

The neuro-fuzzy prediction model is implemented to estimate the gap between the initial model and the uncertain model for 1-year simulation by hourly frequency. Then, the uncertain parameters are implemented on the validated model. The trained model was validated against a calibrated shoebox case study, which represents a large commercial building retrofitted to nZEB standards. Calibration followed ASHRAE Guideline 14 protocols [65], with model performance evaluated using R^2 , mean absolute error, and peak deviation metrics.

2.5.1. Shoe case

A shoebox model of a large commercial building located in Climate Zone 5A is selected as the verification model. The model is assumed to implement retrofitting to achieve a nZEB standard, following the design approach presented in [66]. The construction materials used in the simulation are based on the specifications provided in [66] represented in Table 10.

The building is modeled using EnergyPlus version 9.2.0 and validated based on its energy consumption. The system upgrades are implemented to enhance the HVAC performance, following the methodology described in the configuration of the HVAC system used in the shoebox model is presented in Table 11.

The EnergyPlus model is validated by real building data using the criteria defined in ASHRAE Guideline 14–2002 and ASHRAE Standard 2014 [65], considering the building's initial HVAC system. Following validation, the model is retrofitted to incorporate a multi-source HVAC system for the case study. Due to the high variability in occupancy within the terminal building, the operations of the HVAC systems are significantly influenced by the internal heat and moisture loads generated by occupants. In initial simulation, the average number of occupants is used to define the building's baseline occupancy conditions in the EnergyPlus model. Subsequently, the Sobol sequence is employed to generate stochastic occupancy schedules and MR. The deviation between the stochastic model and the baseline model is then used to calculate the BEPG and IEQ gap.

3. Results

To assess the impacts of occupancy parameters in BPGs, SA was conducted across various use cases. The results of SA were subsequently utilized in the second step to train prediction model. Accordingly, the SA analysis outcomes are presented based on building performance indicators. Following this, the results of prediction model and verification of the framework are discussed in this section.

3.1. SA

SA was utilized to evaluate the role of each parameter in BPGs. Accordingly, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined to track building performance during simulations. We implement the DEUI and indoor air temperature as the KPIs to evaluate the impacts of occupancy

Fig. 8. Duration curve of DEUI for different use cases: a) Small hotel, b) Large hotel, c) Health center, d) Small office, e) Medium office, f) Large office, g) School, and h) Restaurant.

parameters on BEPG and IEQ, respectively.

3.1.1. DEUI

By implementing stochastic inputs related to OD and MR on various types of buildings' simulations, DEUI is calculated for 1-year simulations based on 10-minute frequency. Two different stochastic data are defined as the inputs based on random and Sobol functions to implement OFAT and VBSA, respectively. Additionally, 3 different setpoint temperature are implemented in this investigation to evaluate the performance of buildings based on different setpoints. Therefore, the DEUI in different

scenarios are studied based on duration curve diagram to evaluate the reliability of simulation in design step. The results of the duration curve diagram for 1-year simulation of different scenarios are represented in Fig. 8.

The impact of setpoints on energy performance, relative to the standard baseline, is highlighted in Fig. 8. Accordingly, adjusting setpoints in most non-residential buildings significantly influences heating and cooling demands, reflected in variations in DEUI. An increase in the setpoint leads to a rise in maximum energy demand, emphasizing redesign and retrofitting of building systems for supporting these

Fig. 9. DEUI gap for 1 year simulation – box plot of data for different use cases based on various scenarios: a) Random OD, b) Random activity, and c) Sobol.

changes. The other parameters affect DEUI within a moderate range, while the peak energy requirement remains consistent.

Comparing the results of different scenarios in use cases illustrates the impact of changing setpoints in peak energy demand, especially in high-energy buildings consisting of large hotel, large office, and hospital. Random schedules cause notable difference in DEUI, demonstrating the importance of occupancy-based control strategies.

OD is mentioned in the study to implement uncertainty in occupancy schedules in different building categories simulations. The differences between standard simulations and random OD with the same average as standard approach are considered as DEUI gap illustrated in Fig. 9. As we have different number of occupancy groups in the use cases, the average of different random OD is represented in Fig. 9a to simplify different categories. MR is investigated to demonstrate the role of occupancy activities in BEPG. Implementing random MR in simulation results in DEUI gap in different building categories is represented in Fig. 9b.

To analyze the roles of OD and MR simultaneously, the Sobol function is utilized to implement VBSA and generate inputs for the training datasets. Fig. 9c illustrates the results of buildings' DEUI gaps based on provided inputs by Sobol function.

In Fig. 9a there is a stable pattern of DEUI gaps exhibited in stacked time series and box plots of small hotel and small office buildings, indicating lower sensitivity to random OD variations. The large hotel, offices, and restaurants demonstrate a wider spread and a higher frequency of extreme deviations, mentioning the importance of OD impacts on BEPG. While the hospital and school have a more compact Inter-Quartile Range (IQR), the results demonstrate notable outliers, suggesting occasional disruptions related to OD uncertainties affect their DEUI gap.

From the data in Fig. 9b, it is apparent that the hospital, large hotel, and medium office show a wider IQR, demonstrating higher DEUI gap fluctuations under random MR, while smaller buildings, including small hotel, office, and restaurant exhibit narrower distribution, showing more reliable DEUI in standard simulation. While the amplitude of the

DEUI gap percentage in various categories is different, all categories have a median close to zero, implying that on average, the DEUI of standard models for annual studies is not influenced by the uncertainty related to occupancy MR. However, high variance in time series data mentioned operational unreliability in some cases.

Fig. 9c illustrates the percentage gap in DEUI over a one-year simulation when the Sobol function is used to generate inputs related to OD and MR. This analysis insights on how occupant-related parameters influence BEPG. The small hotel and small office show minimal IQR and box lengths, indicating that they have the most reliable DEUI in standard simulations. In contrast, the large hotel, offices, restaurant, and school demonstrate significant variability, with medians close to zero. This suggests that there are deviations from the baseline in each time step, although the annual data for the baseline remains reliable.

A comparison of the results illustrated in Fig. 9 represents more structured fluctuations in time series data for Sobol function, reducing the sharp variations seen with the other randomness. The implementation of the Sobol function results in the maximum DEUI, emphasizing the role of interaction between OD and MR in the simulation approach. To support these findings, a quantitative assessment has been conducted using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), detailed in Table 12.

Table 12 presents the ANOVA results for the percentage gap in DEUI across various stochastic occupancy methods, including random occupancy schedules, random MR, and the Sobol function. The scenarios simulate various building types, offering a broad view of how occupancy uncertainty affects BEPG. Simulating multiple buildings based on the Sobol function demonstrates more structured and bounded fluctuations in DEUI gaps than random scenarios. This is remarkable in the narrower range between minimum and maximum DEUI gaps under Sobol simulations. Comparing the minimum gap in different scenarios represents that the Sobol function restricts the minimum gap compared to other random methods but still covers the whole period of possibilities for occupancy conditions. Focusing on the highest Sum of Squares (SS) and Mean Squares (MS) observed in the Sobol-based simulations—particularly in the restaurant, school, and office scenarios—highlights that the

Fig. 9. (continued).

Sobol method effectively captures high variability in cases with structurally complex interactions.

3.1.2. Indoor air temperature

Indoor air temperature was analyzed during the simulation of various scenarios to assess the impact of occupancy behavior on IEQ. Accordingly, the results of 1-year simulation of different buildings by 10-minute frequency were examined and summarized to monthly variation represented in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 represents a box plot illustrating the distribution of daily mean indoor air temperatures of different use cases, considering various

uncertainties and the baseline scenario. Compared to the baseline, scenarios involving random schedule, random activity, and Sobol function inputs lead to an increase in indoor air temperature across the use cases. Elevating indoor air temperature due to stochastic occupant presence and associated internal gains, highlights the impact of occupancy activities and schedules in heat loads, resulting in IEQ gap.

The observed increase in indoor air temperature, ranging from 0.5 °C to 1 °C under stochastic conditions, demonstrates about 5 % performance gap because of internal gain based on occupancy impacts. While the occupancy schedule and activity patterns were fixed equal to the baseline scenario, changing indoor temperature setpoints resulted in

Table 12
ANOVA results of DEUI gap percentage for various occupancy random functions.

Scenario Bldgs.	Random occupancy schedules					Random MR					Sobol				
	SS*	MS**	Max	Mean	Min	SS*	MS**	Max	Mean	Min	SS*	MS**	Max	Mean	Min
Small hotel	8.69 e ²	0.017	0.89	-0.05	-0.99	1.42 e ⁵	2.70	13.80	0.11	-6.65	1.22 e ⁶	23.13	18.95	0.36	-11.49
Large hotel	1.43 e ⁸	2.71 e ³	1388	7.55	-90.78	1.58 e ⁸	3.003 e ³	943.8	14.98	-91.57	1.83 e ⁸	3.49 e ³	653.4	8.1	-95.26
Hospital	8.02 e ⁶	1.53 e ²	125	2.58	-45.25	8.05 e ⁶	1.53 e ²	127	2.75	-45.88	3.47 e ⁶	66	58.02	-0.34	-36.99
Small office	1.28 e ⁶	24.36	249.5	0.22	-100	4.1 e ⁵	7.81	238.5	0.069	-100	1.15 e ⁵	21.93	250	0.21	-100
Medium office	4.2 e ⁷	801.8	253.2	3.5	-100	5.6 e ⁷	1067	249.9	4.49	-100	4.4 e ⁷	844	250	3.7	-100
Large office	1.72 e ⁹	3.2 e ⁴	268.2	7.31	-100	9.8 e ⁶	185.9	293.5	-0.034	-100	4.8 e ⁹	844	250	8.11	-100
School	5.56 e ⁹	1.06 e ⁵	243.5	2.89	-99.2	5.90 e ⁹	1.12 e ⁵	263.2	1.93	-103.2	4.65 e ⁹	8.85 e ⁴	272.1	1.93	-99.7
Restaurant	8.05 e ⁹	1.5 e ⁵	119.8	43.6	-106.9	2.3 e ⁹	4.4 e ⁴	95.1	15.44	-96.52	1.01 e ¹⁰	1.93 e ⁵	156.6	50.49	-101.5

* Sum of Squares (SS)

** Mean Square (MS)

Fig. 10. Indoor air temperature for 1 year simulation – box plot of data for monthly indoor temperature of various use cases based on different scenarios: a) Baseline, b) Random OD, c) Random activity, d) Sobol, e) Min. temperature, and f) Max. temperature.

Fig. 11. DEUI for 1 year simulation of calibrated model – a) Timeseries data based on secondly frequency, b) Average hourly profile over one year, and c) Scatter plot of prediction vs. monitoring.

corresponding changes in indoor temperature to align with the new setpoints. When the model was simulated with the updated setpoints, the indoor temperatures closely followed the new setpoints, exhibiting a similar temporal pattern to that of the baseline. Changing the setpoints alters the energy demand of buildings, which, in turn, explains the variation in the duration curves of DEUI across different buildings and setpoints, as illustrated in Fig. 8.

3.2. Prediction model and verification

The proposed framework results in developing neuro-fuzzy prediction model to estimate DEUI gap and the indoor air temperature gap. To achieve this, the DEUI and indoor air temperature values from different models are represented to capture the gaps in these parameters. Based on the SA results, the standard models provide reliable estimates of energy demand and IEQ during the design phase. However, the operational uncertainties influence BPGs and result in reducing reliability of standard simulations in detailed assessments. Consequently, the prediction model must account for BPGs with greater precision. Accordingly, the results of the calibrated model in 2 different conditions, defined by the initial simulation and the Sobol function, are analyzed by secondly frequency to identify BPGs. The neuro-fuzzy model's predictions of BPGs, also evaluated at secondly resolution, illustrate the discrepancies between actual gaps (from the calibrated model) and the predicted ones. Considering the DEUI as one of the investigated parameters, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 present the prediction results based on initial simulation and prediction model.

Fig. 11 presents a comparison between the validated EnergyPlus model with standard occupancy conditions and the corresponding model subjected to random occupancy schedules and MR, derived from the Sobol function. Based on the average hourly profile of DEUI, the standard simulation results show consistent and reliable patterns over

the one-year simulation period. An R^2 value of 77 % shows the potential of the standard simulation in representing the building conditions under uncertainties. However, the minimum and maximum timestep errors are equal to -107% and 111% respectively, highlight the potential risk of failure in timestep-level evaluations. The average error in DEUI under these uncertainties is 18.2% , emphasizing the significant influence of OB parameters on BEPG. To address this issue, a prediction model has been developed based on the provided framework to reduce the timestep-level error and the whole year average. After simulating the prediction model, the results from the validated EnergyPlus model under standard occupancy conditions were integrated with those from the prediction model. Specifically, the DEUI and indoor air temperature obtained from the standard simulation were combined with the DEUI gap and indoor air temperature gap predicted by the prediction model. Accordingly, the prediction model enhances the reliability of building simulations in the presence of OB-related uncertainties.

Fig. 12 represents the results of integrating the prediction model and the validated EnergyPlus model under standard occupancy conditions. Adding the prediction model helps to predict peak DEUI values during simulations, resulting in enhancing model accuracy in the presence of uncertainties. The average hourly profile demonstrates a reduced error in comparison with the standard simulation, highlighting the role of prediction model in improving reliability of standard simulation. An R^2 value of 86% confirms that the standard simulation can be improved by employing the prediction model developed using the proposed framework. At the timestep level, the minimum and maximum errors were calculated equal to -93% and 97% , respectively, indicating a 15% improvement in simulation accuracy compared to standard model. This improvement could be further enhanced with a larger training dataset. Overall, the whole-year average DEUI accuracy is improved by 16.24% compared to the standard model, reducing the annual average DEUI error rate to 1.96% .

Fig. 12. DEUI for 1 year simulation of prediction model – a) Timeseries data based on secondly frequency, b) Average hourly profile over one year, and c) Scatter plot of prediction vs. monitoring.

Indoor air temperature is also predicted as part of the proposed framework. Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 show the indoor air temperature of the shoe case as a result of the initial simulation and the prediction model, respectively.

Fig. 13 shows the reliability of standard simulation in estimating the indoor air temperature of a shoe case under uncertainties related to occupancy schedules and MR introduced using the Sobol function in monitoring results. Specifically, Fig. 13b presents the average hourly indoor temperature profile, emphasizing the standard simulation's capability in capturing the average thermal comfort of the building. Considering the scatter plot and R^2 value of 65.1 % highlight the standard model effectiveness in representing indoor thermal comfort under uncertain conditions. The average error is calculated as 1.5 %, while the maximum and minimum errors are estimated at 12 % and -27 %, respectively, based on time series analysis. These findings suggest that further attention should be given to uncertainties associated with OB in frequency-based assessments.

Fig. 14 illustrates the performance of the prediction model in estimating indoor air temperature, complementing the standard simulation. However, the standard simulation demonstrates acceptable accuracy in capturing average daily temperature, adding prediction model enhances its capability under dynamic conditions. The integration of prediction model and standard model reduces the maximum and minimum errors from 12 % and -27 % (in the standard simulation) to 11 % and -23.6 %, respectively. Additionally, the R^2 value increases to 72 % indicating a stronger correlation between predicted and monitored values. Accordingly, the prediction model improves the performance of standard simulation in predicting indoor thermal comfort conditions, especially in the shoe case.

4. Discussion

Several research have shown that OB plays a key role in the failure to meet design predictions in buildings, commonly referred to as BPGs. The primary objective of this research was developing a framework for quantifying the impact of OB parameters on BPGs. This framework could be implemented after building design, based on standards and regulations, to identify potential performance gaps related to OB. Moreover, actual building condition monitored through digital systems in smart buildings can be incorporated into the framework to estimate initial performance gaps without the need to regenerate the simulation.

This study set out with the aim of assessing extreme OB conditions that lead to BPGs and providing a data-driven framework for estimating BPGs under OB-related uncertainties. The first question in this study sought to assess the impact of OB parameters in BPGs. The findings indicate that, under extreme uncertainty, occupancy schedules and metabolic rates can account for up to 50 % of the energy performance gap (based on the average difference in DEUI across various standard cases), while their influence on indoor air temperature deviation is limited to a maximum of 5 %. Although the frequency of BEPG can vary by up to 100 %, the maximum energy demand of a building can still be predicted by standard simulation, demonstrating the reliability of standard models during the design step. Among OB parameters, setpoint temperature was identified as the most influential factor in determining energy demand, as shown through duration curve analyses of multiple case scenarios.

The second phase of this research involved designing a predictive framework for BPGs based on OB parameters. The provided data-driven framework developed using a neuro-fuzzy system, which employed the simulation-based data examined in the first phase. The initial framework was developed and verified using a shoe case study. As the results of

Fig. 13. Indoor air temperature for 1 year simulation of calibrated model – a) Timeseries data based on secondly frequency, b) Average hourly profile over one year, and c) Scatter plot of prediction vs. monitoring.

implementing the neuro-fuzzy framework in predicting BPGs, the standard simulation of shoe case is improved by 16.24 % in predicting building energy performance and 5 % in predicting indoor temperatures. The results of the prediction model related to BPGs are added to the building's standard simulation at each time step, thereby enhancing the accuracy of building energy performance prediction.

To apply the developed prediction framework, the OB parameters, including occupancy schedules, occupancy activity, and setpoint temperature, must first be identified. By implementing these inputs into the prediction framework, the potential gaps in DEUI and indoor air temperature compared to design expectations is determined. In the final step, the results of the prediction model are integrated with the design-phase simulation to update the input assumptions, thereby reducing performance gap risks. Although these results highlight the potential of the proposed framework to enhance the accuracy of building performance simulation tools, its current application is limited to simulation-based analyses. On the other hand, we examined only five categories as the initial categories, considered as a limitation in terms of representativeness. However, our primary contribution lies in developing a generalizable framework for improving learning in a global context. Importantly, the framework was validated on a terminal case that was not among the initial categories, thereby demonstrating applicability beyond the predefined scope. Expanding the framework through integration with experimental monitoring systems and refinement of the data-driven model could yield more practical insights and broader applicability. Furthermore, the framework has the potential to be extended to involve additional BPG-related parameters, enabling quantification of their impacts and comprehensive investigation of BPGs. This approach led us to reduce uncertainties under varying

operational conditions.

5. Conclusion

This study set out to develop a framework for predicting the impact of various occupancy-related causal factors in BPGs. The first step focused on evaluating the impact of OB parameters in BEPG and IAQ gap. Three independent OB parameters, including occupancy schedule, occupancy activity, and setpoint temperature, are studied. Eight different nonresidential standard buildings are defined to evaluate the impact of these parameters in BPGs. The results indicated that setpoint temperature is a critical parameter during the design phase, particularly in determining the building's energy demand. In contrast, other parameters, including OD and MR, showed limited direct influence on energy demand. However, frequency analysis represents that OB can affect the DEUI and indoor air temperature by up to 100 % and 5 %, respectively. These findings highlight the need to enhance building performance simulation tools to account for such impacts more accurately.

The main goal of the current study was to develop a prediction framework for quantifying the impact of OB parameters in BPGs. Accordingly, the results of evaluating the impact of OB parameters in BEPG and IAQ gap is employed in neuro-fuzzy system for developing a prediction framework. By integrating the proposed prediction framework as an extension, the BPGs in simulation tools can be reduced based on the quantified effects of OB parameters. This framework extends the conventional simulation workflow by introducing a prediction model based on possible OB related uncertainties, where the BPGs predicted by the model are used to enhance baseline simulation, ultimately

Fig. 14. Indoor air temperature for 1 year simulation of prediction model – a) Timeseries data based on secondly frequency, b) Average hourly profile over one year, and c) Scatter plot of prediction vs. monitoring.

improving the accuracy and reliability of energy performance forecasts. When applied to both the BEPG and the indoor air temperature gap, the results across different conditions in the employed shoe case demonstrated significant improvement. The results of this investigation show that implementing prediction framework in the presence of stochastic OB parameters reduced the impact of these uncertainties in BEPG from 18.2 % to 1.96 %. Similarly, the influence of these parameters on the maximum indoor air temperature gap was reduced by 3.4 % using the prediction framework.

These findings suggest that the neuro-fuzzy prediction framework play an integral part in enhancing building performance simulation tools by incorporating the effects of uncertain parameters related to OB. While the simulation tools continue to evolve, the integration of data-driven approaches can improve accuracy without the need to regenerate simulations. To understand the role and potential of proposed framework in future building simulation tools, further research is needed. Expanding the proposed framework across a broader set of categories and building archetypes, including real-time applications in diverse climates and occupancy conditions, helps for establishing broader generalizability and policy relevance. In particular, experimental investigations using digital twin systems and real-time monitoring data are essential to evaluate the performance and applicability of such frameworks under real-world conditions. Moreover, coupling this approach with large-scale datasets such as urban building energy models or digital twins may further improve its predictive power and generalizability.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ahmad Esmailzadeh: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.
Mohamed Hamdy: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Grammarly to improve language and readability. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

The author(s) disclosed receipt of the following financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article: This project, Green Deal - ARV, a Horizon Europe-funded project, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101036723.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] P.X.W. Zou, X. Xu, J. Sanjayan, J. Wang, Review of 10 years research on building energy performance gap: Life-cycle and stakeholder perspectives, *Energy Build.* 178 (2018) 165–181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.08.040>.
- [2] M. Andargie, M. Lin, J.D. Barbosa, E. Azar, *Holistic building performance evaluation: an integrated Post-Occupancy Evaluation and Energy Modeling (POEEM) Framework*, *Constr. Res. Congr.* 007 (1994) (2020) 809–818.
- [3] Y. Bai, C. Yu, W. Pan, Systematic examination of energy performance gap in low-energy buildings, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 202 (July) (2024) 114701, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114701>.
- [4] C.K. Metallidou, K.E. Psannis, E.A. Egyptiadou, Energy efficiency in smart buildings: IoT approaches, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 63679–63699, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2984461>.
- [5] D. Yilmaz, A.M. Tanyer, L.D. Toker, A data-driven energy performance gap prediction model using machine learning, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 181 (May) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113318>.
- [6] S. Cozza, J. Chambers, A. Brambilla, M.K. Patel, In search of optimal consumption: a review of causes and solutions to the Energy Performance Gap in residential buildings, *Energy Build.* 249 (2021) 111253, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111253>.
- [7] X. Wu, B. Lin, G. Papachristos, P. Liu, N. Zimmermann, A holistic approach to evaluate building performance gap of green office buildings: a case study in China, *Build. Environ.* 175 (October 2019) (2020) 106819, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.106819>.
- [8] T.A. Reddy, Literature review on calibration of building energy simulation programs: uses, problems, procedures, uncertainty, and tools, *ASHRAE Trans.* 112 (1) (2006).
- [9] M.S. Gerald, E. Ghisi, Building-level and stock-level in contrast: a literature review of the energy performance of buildings during the operational stage, *Energy Build.* 211 (2020) 109810, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2020.109810>.
- [10] N. Jain, E. Burman, S. Stamp, D. Mumovic, M. Davies, Cross-sectoral assessment of the performance gap using calibrated building energy performance simulation, *Energy Build.* 224 (2020) 110271, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110271>.
- [11] H. Yoshino, T. Hong, N. Nord, IEA EBC annex 53: Total energy use in buildings—Analysis and evaluation methods, *Energy Build.* 152 (2017) 124–136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2017.07.038>.
- [12] J. Vivian, L. Carnieletto, M. Cover, M. De Carli, At the roots of the energy performance gap: Analysis of monitored indoor air before and after building retrofits, *Build. Environ.* 246 (July) (2023) 110914, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110914>.
- [13] Z. Zheng, J. Zhou, Z. Jiaqin, Y. Yang, F. Xu, H. Liu, Review of the building energy performance gap from simulation and building lifecycle perspectives: magnitude, causes and solutions, *Dev. Built Environ.* 17 (January) (2024) 100345, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2024.100345>.
- [14] P. de Wilde, Ten questions concerning building performance analysis, *Build. Environ.* 153 (2019) 110–117, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2019.02.019>.
- [15] N. Zare, S.M.E. Saryazdi, A.M. Bahman, A. Shafaat, M. Sartipour, Investigation of heating energy performance gap (EPG) in design and operation stages of residential buildings, *Energy Build.* 301 (October) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113747>.
- [16] A. Reguis, M. Tunzi, B. Vand, P. Tuohy, J. Currie, Energy performance of Scottish public buildings and its impact on the ability to use low-temperature heat, *Energy Build.* 290 (December 2022) (2023) 113064, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113064>.
- [17] P.X.W. Zou, M. Alam, Closing the building energy performance gap through component level analysis and stakeholder collaborations, *Energy Build.* 224 (2020) 110276, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110276>.
- [18] W. Miller, B. Sodagar, D. Whaley, K. Bamdad, and S. Zedan, Mind the gap: A comparison of socio-technical limitations of national house rating systems in the UK and Australia, 43 Jan. 28502BC, doi: 10.1016/j.job.2021.102570.
- [19] N.A. Khan, B. Bhattacharjee, Thermal and noise insulation performance interaction of building envelope during building simulation optimization in tropical climates, *Build. Environ.* 200 (2021) 107948, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2021.107948>.
- [20] M. Alam, V.M. Phung, P.X.W. Zou, J. Sanjayan, Risk identification and assessment for construction and commissioning stages of building energy retrofit projects. 22nd International Conference of Advancement of Construction Management and Real Estate, Melbourne, Australia, 2017.
- [21] P. De Wilde, The gap between predicted and measured energy performance of buildings: a framework for investigation, *Autom. Constr.* 41 (2014) 40–49, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2014.02.009>.
- [22] A.C. Menezes, A. Cripps, D. Bouchlaghem, R. Buswell, Predicted vs. actual energy performance of non-domestic buildings: using post-occupancy evaluation data to reduce the performance gap, *Appl. Energy* 97 (2012) 355–364, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.11.075>.
- [23] N. Delgarm, B. Sajadi, K. Azarbad, S. Delgarm, Sensitivity analysis of building energy performance: a simulation-based approach using OFAT and variance-based sensitivity analysis methods, *J. Build. Eng.* 15 (December 2017) (2018) 181–193, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2017.11.020>.
- [24] E. Mocanu, P.H. Nguyen, M. Gibescu, W.L. Kling, Comparison of machine learning methods for estimating energy consumption in buildings, in: 2014 Int. Conf. Probabilistic Methods Appl. to Power Syst. PMAPS 2014 - Conf. Proc., 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PMAPS.2014.6960635>.
- [25] D. Cali, T. Osterhage, R. Streblow, D. Müller, Energy performance gap in refurbished German dwellings: lesson learned from a field test, *Energy Build.* 127 (2016) 1146–1158, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.05.020>.
- [26] Y. Kim, A. Kim, J.Y. Chung, Population pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic modeling of delayed effect of escitalopram-induced QT prolongation, *J. Affect. Disord.* 285 (2021) 120–126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAD.2021.02.048>.
- [27] S.R. Thompson, L.E. Compton, M.L. Fang, J.L. Chen, Pharmacologic treatment of antidepressant-induced excessive sweating: a systematic review, *Rev. Psychiatr. Clin.* 48 (1) (2021) 57–65, <https://doi.org/10.15761/0101-60830000000279>.
- [28] E. Ono, Z.D. Tekler, K.P. Lam, Y. Jin, D. Yan, A. Chong, Evaluating the sensitivity and robustness of occupancy models for building energy simulation during design, *Build. Environ.* 261 (January) (2024) 111739, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111739>.
- [29] S. El Khattabi, G. Fraisse, A. Leconte, S. Rouchier, Impact of occupant behavior on optimal multi-objective solutions for the design of low-energy buildings, *Energy Build.* 317 (June) (2024) 114371, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114371>.
- [30] J. Bielskus, V. Motuzienė, The Influence of Schedules of Open Office Occupants' Presence on Building's Energy Demand, in: *Environmental Engineering. Proceedings of the International Conference on Environmental Engineering, ICEE, 2020*, pp. 1–7.
- [31] B. Simanic, B. Nordquist, H. Bagge, D. Johansson, Predicted and measured user-related energy usage in newly built low-energy schools in Sweden, *J. Build. Eng.* 29 (2020) 101142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JOBE.2019.101142>.
- [32] G. Papachristos, et al., Low carbon building performance in the construction industry: a multi-method approach of project management operations and building energy use applied in a UK public office building, *Energy Build.* 206 (2020) 109609, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2019.109609>.
- [33] V.M. Barthelme, C. Becchio, V. Fabi, S.P. Corgnati, Occupant behaviour lifestyles and effects on building energy use: Investigation on high and low performing building features, *Energy Procedia* 140 (2017) 93–101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.11.126>.
- [34] M. Pappalardo, T. Reverdy, “Explaining the performance gap in a French energy efficient building: Persistent misalignment between building design, space occupancy and operation practices,” *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 70 (September) (2020) 101809, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101809>.
- [35] Q. Ali, M.J. Thaheem, F. Ullah, S.M.E. Sepasgozar, The performance gap in energy-efficient office buildings: how the occupants can help? *Energies* 13 (6) (2020) 1–27, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13061480>.
- [36] A. Chong, G. Augenbroe, D. Yan, Occupancy data at different spatial resolutions: Building energy performance and model calibration, *Appl. Energy* 286 (January) (2021) 116492, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116492>.
- [37] A. Bahadori-Jahromi, R. Salem, A. Mylona, A.U. Hasan, H. Zhang, The effect of occupants' behaviour on the building performance gap: UK residential case studies, *Sustain* 14 (3) (2022) 1–18, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031362>.
- [38] X. Chen, T. Guo, M. Kriegel, P. Geyer, A hybrid-model forecasting framework for reducing the building energy performance gap, *Adv. Eng. Informatics* 52 (October 2021) (2022) 101627, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2022.101627>.
- [39] J. Vivian, L. Carnieletto, M. Cover, M. De Carli, At the roots of the energy performance gap: Analysis of monitored indoor air before and after building retrofits, *Build. Environ.* 246 (October) (2023) 110914, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110914>.
- [40] L.M. Obeidat, S. Al Nusair, S. Ma'bdeh, R. Bataineh, Redefining realistic and stochastic occupancy schedules and patterns for residential buildings in Jordan, *Energy* 313 (July) (2024) 133641, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.133641>.
- [41] V. Vámos, M. Horváth, The effect of building refurbishment and changing occupancy on the district heating consumption of multifamily buildings: Case study of Miskolc, Hungary, *J. Build. Eng.* 81 (June) (2023) 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2023.108132>.
- [42] S. Chen, et al., Characterizing energy-related occupant behavior towards urban residential buildings in China with statistical database establishment, *Energy Build.* 324 (August) (2024) 114889, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114889>.
- [43] H. Hosamo, G.B.A. Coelho, C. Nordahl Rolfsen, D. Kraniotis, Building performance optimization through sensitivity Analysis, and economic insights using AI, *Energy Build.* 325 (November) (2024) 114999, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114999>.
- [44] H. Yu, X. Xu, Reinforcement learning for occupant behavior modeling in public buildings: why, what and how? *J. Build. Eng.* 96 (April) (2024) 110491, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2024.110491>.
- [45] Z. Zheng, J. Zhou, Y. Jin, Y. Yang, F. Xu, H. Liu, An integrated model of the driving mechanism for the building energy performance gap, *J. Build. Eng.* 96 (April) (2024) 110610, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2024.110610>.
- [46] Y. Seo Yoo, H. Shin, D. Woo Kim, C. Soo Park, Performance gap analysis for Korean building energy efficiency certification, *Energy Build.* 314 (April) (2024) 114294, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114294>.
- [47] S. Kim, C.S. Park, Customized causal modeling of occupant behaviors in residential households: Causal sufficiency vs. data sufficiency, *Energy Build.* 329 (November 2024) (2025) 115233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.115233>.

- [48] S. Hu, D. Yan, E. Azar, F. Guo, A systematic review of occupant behavior in building energy policy, *Build. Environ.* 175 (2020) 106807, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2020.106807>.
- [49] A. Mahdavi et al., The role of occupants in buildings' energy performance gap: Myth or reality?, 13(6) (2021).
- [50] "Functional Mock-Up Unit Import in EnergyPlus For Authors , Thierry Stephane Nouidui , Michael Wetter , Wangda Zuo Environmental Energy and Technologies Division August 2013 Proceedings of BS2013 : 13th Conference of International Building Performance Simu," no. August, (2013).
- [51] "No Title." <https://www.energycodes.gov/>.
- [52] EnergyPlus Co-simulation Toolbox.
- [53] Prototype Building Models | Building Energy Codes Program. <https://www.energycodes.gov/prototype-building-models> (accessed Jan. 02, 2025).
- [54] P.A.M.P. Kemme, S. Workspere, J.L. M. Hensen, M.H.H. Mohamed, B. Tuip, Building portfolio analysis and benchmarking for estimating energy saving potential.
- [55] A. Persily, A. Musser, S. Emmerich, M. Taylor, Simulations of Indoor Air Quality and Ventilation Impacts of Demand Controlled Ventilation in Commercial and Institutional Buildings., *Natl. Inst. Stand. Technol.*, (August) (2003), [Online]. Available: <http://fire.nist.gov/bfrlpubs/build03/PDF/b03074.pdf>.
- [56] R. Hendron, J. Burch, Development of standardized domestic hot water event schedules for residential buildings, *Proc. Energy Sustain. Conf.* 2007 (2009) 531–539, <https://doi.org/10.1115/ES2007-36104>.
- [57] V. Fabi, R.V. Andersen, S. Corgnati, B.W. Olesen, Occupants' window opening behaviour: a literature review of factors influencing occupant behaviour and models, *Build. Environ.* 58 (2012) 188–198, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2012.07.009>.
- [58] A. Mahdavi, F. Tahmasebi, Predicting people's presence in buildings: an empirically based model performance analysis, *Energy Build.* 86 (2015) 349–355, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2014.10.027>.
- [59] H. Dai, M. Ye, Variance-based global sensitivity analysis for multiple scenarios and models with implementation using sparse grid collocation, *J. Hydrol.* 528 (2015) 286–300, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2015.06.034>.
- [60] A. Ioannou, L.C.M. Itard, Energy performance and comfort in residential buildings: Sensitivity for building parameters and occupancy, *Energy Build.* 92 (2015) 216–233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2015.01.055>.
- [61] T. Wei, A review of sensitivity analysis methods in building energy analysis, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 20 (2013) 411–419, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2012.12.014>.
- [62] "Standard 55 – Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy." <https://www.ashrae.org/technical-resources/bookstore/standard-55-thermal-environmental-conditions-for-human-occupancy> (accessed Jun. 19, 2024).
- [63] M. Jradi, et al., ObepME: an online building energy performance monitoring and evaluation tool to reduce energy performance gaps, *Energy Build.* 166 (2018) 196–209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2018.02.005>.
- [64] A.I. Dounis, C. Caraiscos, Advanced control systems engineering for energy and comfort management in a building environment—A review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 13 (6–7) (2009) 1246–1261, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2008.09.015>.
- [65] ASHRAE, Measurement of energy and demand savings. (2002).
- [66] A. Esmailzadeh, B. Deal, A. Yousefi-Koma, M.R. Zakerzadeh, How combination of control methods and renewable energies leads a large commercial building to a zero-emission zone – a case study in U.S, *Energy* 263 (PD) (2023) 125944, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.125944>.
- [67] K. Dakhili, A.Y. Koma, A. Esmailzadeh, Improving the Performance of a Small-Scale CHP Plant using Fuzzy Sliding Mode Controller, in: 2019 7th International Conference on Robotics and Mechatronics (ICRoM), 2019, pp. 577–582, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRoM48714.2019.9071912>.